

Trumbull Creek Project, Ashtabula County (41.66180, -80.99040)

Since construction in 2023, the main nutrient benefit of the Trumbull Creek Project has been runoff prevention due to conversion from an agricultural field and removal as a nutrient source, preventing approximately 0.6 lbs phosphorus export per acre each year. Little to no “new” nutrient inputs are filtered by this Project because it is in the middle of a watershed divide (Mill Creek, Bronson Creek) and lacks direct connection to nutrient inputs, and neither factor is likely to change. Soil minerals have the capacity to sorb additional phosphate, although some may be released under anoxic conditions. Continued surveillance for transient phosphate release is needed, particularly during mid-winter thaws when anoxic water containing released nutrients may be exported.

Surface Water Flow

The hydrology at this Project is passively managed. The Project has 30 acres of restored wetland. Water enters as precipitation and moves slowly across constructed hummock-hollow microtopography towards the outlet at the north of the Project, ultimately flowing into a tributary of Mill Creek in the Grand River watershed. Although water generally flows south to north, there are no discrete flow paths within this Project. The outflow water level control structure is an Agri Drain which maintains the maximum height of the water in the wetland. A hydrologic event at this Project is defined as > 0.5 inches of rain within 48 hours as tracked by nearest USGS gage.

Nutrient Retention

Converted Farmfield Area	Phosphorus Loss Prevented Annually	
	Per Acre	Total (Mean ± SD)
30 acres	0.6 lbs	19 ± 13 lbs

Enhancement Considerations*

The following practices may yield increased nutrient removal in similar isolated wetland Projects or could be accounted for in future site selection:

- Assess parcel footprint for the ability to capture tile drain, stream, or ditch water inputs, in addition to precipitation, in order to optimize nutrient input potential (i.e., connectivity).
- If nutrient-laden water source is directed toward the site, adjust water level control structure(s) to maximize water retention capacity and retain limited nutrient inputs (i.e., residence time).
- If a small parcel has limited connection to a nutrient-laden water source (e.g., the primary source of water is precipitation), the project may not contribute substantially to watershed scale nutrient load reduction goals.

*All considerations are based on the best available science at this time, and all recommended items may not be feasible given physical constraints, resource limitations, and broader management goals.